

Extending the Community of Inquiry Framework: A Quantitative Study of Online Collaboration, Shared Metacognition, and Core Constructs

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With the increasing practice of online learning, learning has shifted from being primarily individual to increasing collaborative, where groups think, reflect, and regulate knowledge together. This collaborative dimension is reflected in the construct of shared metacognition, an extension of the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework. Despite the flexibility and accessibility of online learning, studies report persistent challenges, including low student satisfaction, poor engagement, feelings of isolation, and weakened social interaction. This study investigates the impact of a semester-long intervention focused on building an online collaborative learning (OCL) environment on undergraduates' shared metacognition and overall CoI. A quantitative survey design was employed to measure perceptions across a large student cohort. A total of 110 undergraduates from two cohorts at a public university in Penang, Malaysia completed an online survey on their perceptions towards the Social Presence (SP), Cognitive Presence (CP), Teaching Presence (TP), and Shared Metacognition (SM) constructs following the intervention. Results revealed that all four CoI constructs were positively perceived, with TP rated the highest. SM emerged as the second most positively perceived construct, indicating a strong awareness of both individual cognitive efforts and collaborative regulation of learning. Moreover, findings revealed the critical role of CP in collaborative knowledge construction. However, SP was the least perceived, with challenges noted in group conflict resolution. The study reinforces the importance of holistic instructional design and extends the CoI framework by highlighting the significance of Shared Metacognition that calls for practical insights for educators to strengthen collaboration, critical thinking, and community building in online learning.

Keywords:

Community of Inquiry (CoI); Online Collaborative Learning (OCL); Social Presence; Cognitive Presence; Teaching Presence; Shared Metacognition; Perceptions

Introduction

Learning goes beyond the individual process of acquiring new knowledge and skills. It is common to have students engage with content on their own, yet deeper understanding often emerged as a result of collaboration, where a group of individuals brainstorm ideas, share perspectives,

challenge differing viewpoints, and regulate their progress as a community (Hung et al., 2023). In higher education, online environments have increasingly become important spaces for this collective process, offering a range of collaborative activities that promote peer learning (Yusof, 2022).

When designed effectively, such environments enable learners to exchange ideas, negotiate meaning, and co-construct knowledge in ways that can even surpass traditional classroom interaction (Belle, 2024).

Community of Inquiry (CoI) Framework

The Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework proposed by Garrison, Anderson, and Archer (2001) centralises on the facilitation of meaningful interaction and engagement in the online learning environments. The framework is built on three interdependent constructs, Cognitive Presence (CP), Social Presence (SP), and Teaching Presence (TP), each plays a critical role in ensuring a rich online learning experience through interpersonal connection, critical inquiry and purposeful teaching (Garrison et al., 2001). In fact, the CoI framework aligns well with Lev Vygotsky's Social Constructivism and George Siemens' Connectivism learning theories, both of which emphasise that knowledge is not constructed in isolation but through social interaction and shared validation of understanding (Garrison, 2009, as cited in Shea et al., 2022).

The Role of Core Constructs in Online Learning

Based on the CoI framework, cognitive presence plays a central role in enabling students to move beyond surface-level participation towards deeper learning. Through discussion, reflection, and problem-solving, this construct provides the space for students to construct meaning and engage critically with ideas (Garrison et al., 2001). Complementing this, social presence creates the conditions that make each inquiry possible by fostering trust, belonging, and

openness among participants. When students feel connected and supported, they are more willing to share perspectives, challenge ideas, and collaborate meaningfully. At the same time, teaching presence through intentional design, structured facilitation, and clear guidance, leading collaborative efforts toward purposeful outcomes, helping students navigate complexity and remain engaged throughout their learning (Garrison et al., 2001). Together, these three constructs interact dynamically, making learning a collaborative and interactive process rather than a solitary one. As Gogus (2023) further explained, strong social bonds encourage deeper cognitive engagement, while well-structured teaching provides the scaffolding for critical inquiry.

Extending CoI with Shared Metacognition

Building on these foundations, scholars have recognised that collaboration requires not only interaction and guidance but also collective responsibility for managing how groups learn together. This recognition has led to the introduction of Shared Metacognition as an extension of the CoI framework in the recent year (Garrison, 2022). Shared Metacognition highlights how learners monitor their collective understanding, adapt relevant strategies, and regulate group progress, ensuring that inquiry is both meaningful and sustained (Garrison, 2022). By integrating this construct, the CoI framework extends beyond individual meaning-making to the collaborative regulation of knowledge construction. This addition is particularly relevant in online environments, where the success of group learning often depends on how effectively students co-regulate their contributions and maintain accountability to shared goals.

Fig. 1 The Revised Community of Inquiry (CoI) Framework (adapted from Garrison, 2022)

Challenges in Online Collaborative Learning

Despite the promise of collaborative online learning, studies reported persistent challenges. Issues such as limited interaction, reduced engagement, and weakened social connectedness have been constantly raised by researchers, all of which can undermine the effectiveness of online learning (Abdul Aziz et al., 2023; Hadi et al., 2022; Mustapha et al., 2022). These issues stress the need for pedagogical approaches that support both individual and collective formation of knowledge within online collaborative environments to foster high-quality, meaningful, and satisfying learning experiences. While the CoI framework has been widely applied to address these concerns, much of the research done in higher education has focused on its original three constructs, leaving Shared Metacognition relatively underexplored (Annamalai, 2017; Liu & Diana Deris, 2022; Patwardharr et al., 2020). On top of that, limited attention has

been given to how students perceive the interplay between Shared Metacognition and the core CoI constructs in practice.

This study seeks to address that gap by extending the CoI framework to examine undergraduate students' perceptions of Social Presence, Cognitive Presence, Teaching Presence, and Shared Metacognition within a semester-long online collaborative learning intervention. By focusing on students' perspectives, this research aims to offer empirical evidence on how the constructs interrelate and how the framework can be enriched to better capture the dynamics of collaborative knowledge building in online learning environments.

Hence, this study contributes to the literature by examining the impact of a semester-long OCL intervention on undergraduates' shared metacognition and overall CoI. It further explores how strategies grounded in the CoI framework can enhance student engagement and strengthen the sense of community

within OCL environments. This study aims to answer the following research question:

In what ways do students feel their experiences in online collaborative learning have influenced their sense of:

- belonging and connection with peers (Social Presence)?
- understanding and reflection on course material (Cognitive Presence)?
- support and guidance from instructors (Teaching Presence)?
- shared thinking and learning strategies (Shared Metacognition)?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design using a survey method to capture students' perceptions of Social Presence, Cognitive Presence, Teaching Presence, and Shared Metacognition following the integration of the CoI model within an OCL environment facilitated through a total of six Google tools, including Google Classrooms, Google Sites, Google Docs, Google Slides, Google Sheets, and Google Forms. The survey approach was selected as it enables the collection of numerical data from a relatively large sample, providing the ease of systematic comparison between the four constructs measured. Moreover, quantitative methods are recognised for their efficiency in data analysis (Connolly, 2007) and their capacity to support the generalisation of findings to broader populations (Carr, 1994).

Participants

The participants of this study were drawn from full-time undergraduates enrolled in the Bachelor of Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (TESOL) program under the School of Education.

This group was purposefully selected as they were registered for the course QIMT213E Digital Audio and Video during Semester II of the 2022/2023 and 2023/2024 academic years. A total of 110 students from two cohorts participated without restriction to ensure comprehensive coverage and reduce sampling bias.

Research Instrument

An online survey made up of five sections was designed and administered via Google Forms to measure students' perceptions of the impact of SP, CP, TP, and SM in the OCL environment. It contains a demographic section and a total of 45 construct-related items adapted from Hilliard and Stewart's (2019) and Garrison's (2022) study. Each construct were assessed using a 6-point Likert scale, with the intention to omit the typical 'Neutral' midpoint where participants might potentially select due to indecision, thus affecting the clarity of opinion and reliability of results (Alenxander et al., 2018; Nowlis et al., 2002).

Data Collection & Procedure

The study is conducted based on a three-phase procedure to examine the impact of OCL intervention. The first phase involved the development of an OCL environment using six Google tools. Google Classroom functioned as the central learning management system for administering and managing collaborative teaching and learning. It served as the main platform for announcements, learning materials, supplementary resources, and collaborative activities prepared by the lecturer. Secondly, Google Sites provided structured guideline for the Online Interaction–Collaborative Reflective Writing (OI-CRW) activities. The website educates students on the online

interaction strategies to be applied in their weekly reflective tasks. These tasks required students to engage in group discussions on the taught content and collaboratively produce reflective writing facilitated through Google Docs, which supported peer interaction in the online setting. Google Slides was designed to facilitate peer introductions, while Google Sheets was mainly utilised in tracking attendance and engagement in OI-CRW tasks, and Google Forms supported lecturer for quick knowledge checks throughout the course.

In the second phase, these tools were systematically integrated into a semester-long teaching and learning intervention that lasted for 14 weeks across both cohorts. Participants were allowed to form groups consisting of five to six members and were consistently guided to interact and engage in to OI-CRW activities throughout the semester. In the final phase, following the completion of the intervention, participants completed an online survey designed to capture their perceptions of SP, CP, TP, and SM.

Fig. 2 Summary of research procedure

Data Analysis

Upon the completion of online survey, the data gathered were analysed using descriptive analysis in the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Based on descriptive statistics, this study looked into the frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation of each item to obtain a comprehensive overview of the participants' responses in terms of their perceptions of the four constructs. This approach enabled the identification of general trends, patterns, and variations in how participants experienced the OCL environment. The results were then organised systematically by construct, allowing each section of the questionnaire to be examined in detail. Apart from ensuring the results not only inform about participants' perceptions, this approach also worked well in examining the relative strengths and weaknesses of the OCL intervention across the different CoI dimensions.

Results

Demographics

The participants of this study comprised 110 undergraduates from two cohorts enrolled in the TESOL programme, who had taken the course QIMT213E Digital Audio and Video. Specifically, 5 out of 90 students from Semester II 2022/2023 and 25 out of 55 students from Semester II 2023/2024 voluntarily responded to the survey. Table 1 presents the demographic distribution across gender, age, nationality, and race.

Of the total respondents, 93 were female (84.5%) and 17 were male (15.5%). The majority were aged 21–22 years (87.3%), followed by smaller proportions, 8 participants aged 23–24 years (7.3%), 4 participants aged 19–20 years (3.6%), and 2 participants aged 25 years and above (1.8%). In terms of nationality, local undergraduates dominated the sample with 100 respondents

(90.9%), while non-Malaysian students made up 10 respondents (9.1%). Ethnic distribution showed that Malay students formed the largest group with 75 respondents (68.2%),

followed by Chinese students with 20 (18.2%). The sample also included 6 Indian students (5.5%) and 9 students from other ethnic backgrounds (8.2%).

Table 1

Participants' Demographics

	Demographic Variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	93	84.5
	Male	17	15.5
Age	19-20 years old	4	3.6
	21-22 years old	96	87.3
	23-24 years old	8	7.3
	25 years old and above	2	1.8
Nationality	Malaysian	100	90.9
	Non-Malaysian	10	9.1
Race	Chinese	20	18.2
	Indian	6	5.5
	Malay	75	68.2
	Other	9	8.2

Students' Perception of CoI Construct

Social Presence (SP)

Social presence was perceived positively by participants during the OCL intervention. As shown in Table 2, this construction obtained an overall mean score of 5.21 and a standard deviation of 0.73. The three highest-rated items were SP6 (M = 5.45, SD = 0.85), SP8 (Mean = 5.35, SD = 0.91), and SP5 (Mean = 5.35, SD = 0.88).

Participants strongly agreed that the OCL environment provided the freedom to express their viewpoints (SP6) through the commenting and reply features in Google Docs. This finding affirmed the effectiveness of the intervention in encouraging active participation and open sharing of ideas. Majority of them agreed to have their voice heard and thoughts communicated, as reflected in SP8, "I felt that my point of view was

acknowledged by my group members". At the same time, the OCL environment enabled participants to feel at ease engaging in active contribution of knowledge, as they expressed comfort when participating in the online interaction (SP5).

However, group dynamics were not perceived as strongly. The lowest-rated item was SP9 (M = 4.95), "I felt comfortable disagreeing with my group members while still maintaining a sense of trust". Although the score remained above average, it suggests that students were less comfortable managing disagreements within their groups. Interestingly, SP9 was recorded the highest standard deviation (SD = 1.15), indicating considerable variation in how participants felt about expressing opposing views compared to other forms of interaction in the OCL environment.

Table 2

Mean, and Standard Deviation of Students’ Perceived Social Presence

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall
SP1 I felt that online interaction (in Google Docs) is an excellent medium for social interaction.	5.09	1.08	
SP2 I felt that peer group introductions (in Google Slide) enabled me to form a sense of belonging in the course.	4.98	1.00	
SP3 I felt that getting to know my peers in online interaction (in Google Docs) gave me a sense of belonging in the course.	5.07	1.00	
SP4 I felt comfortable interacting with my group members through the online medium (in Google Docs).	5.33	0.88	M= 5.21 SD= 0.73
SP5 I felt comfortable participating in the online interaction (in Google Docs).	5.35	0.88	
SP6 I felt that I have the chances to express my opinions (in Google Docs).	5.45	0.85	
SP7 I felt that online interaction helped me to develop a sense of collaboration with my group members (in Google Docs).	5.30	0.86	
SP8 I felt that my point of view was acknowledged by my group members (in Google Docs).	5.35	0.91	
SP9 I felt comfortable disagreeing with my group members while still maintaining a sense of trust (in Google Docs).	4.95	1.15	

Cognitive Presence (CP)

Results indicated that all items for CP achieved mean scores above 5, with an overall mean of 5.29 (SD = 0.85). This finding demonstrates consistently a consistent positive perceptions of the OCL intervention in significantly enhanced participants’ cognitive engagement and supported meaningful knowledge construction throughout the semester.

The strongest perception was identified for CP3, “Course activities (OI & CRW) provided a variety of useful information sources to learn more about the topics in digital audio and video course (in Google Docs). ”, with the highest mean score of 5.37 (SD = 0.96). Participants generally agreed that the design and

implementation of course activities were beneficial in providing access to valuable resources that support the learning of course content. Similarly, CP6 (M = 5.36, SD = 0.90) reflected students’ perception that the OCL environment was effective in improving their understanding of the subject matter.

Although the overall perception was highly positive, CP8 recorded the lowest score (M = 5.21, SD = 1.02). Some participants felt less strongly that the OCL intervention fostered higher-order thinking skills, suggesting a weaker perceived connection between the course content and the development of advanced critical inquiry.

Table 3

Mean, and Standard Deviation of Students' Perceived Cognitive Presence

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall
CP1 Course activities (OI & CRW) increased my interest in digital audio and video course (in Google Docs).	5.26	0.96	
CP2 Course activities (OI & CRW) stimulated my curiosity about the weekly topic (in Google Docs).	5.27	0.97	
CP3 Course activities (OI & CRW) provided a variety of useful information sources to learn more about the topics in digital audio and video course (in Google Docs).	5.37	0.96	
CP4 Course activities (OI & CRW) were valuable in helping me appreciate different points of view (in Google Docs).	5.29	0.96	M= 5.29 SD= 0.85
CP5 Course activities (OI & CRW) helped me answer questions raised in learning digital audio and video course (in Google Docs).	5.27	0.98	
CP6 Course activities (OI & CRW) helped me understand fundamental concepts about digital audio and video course (in Google Docs).	5.36	0.90	
CP7 Course activities (OI & CRW) enabled me to explore and integrate ideas into solutions for the final video project.	5.24	0.96	
CP8 Course activities (OI & CRW) equipped me to have higher thinking skills.	5.21	1.02	

Teaching Presence (TP)

As shown in Table 4, all items under TP achieved strikingly high mean scores of 5.4 or above, indicating a strong positive perception of the educational experiences designed throughout the 14-week OCL intervention. Compared with SP and CP, TP stood out as the most highly rated construct, where the strategies implemented to foster this construct were particularly effective.

TP8 emerged as the highest-rated item among all with a mean score of 5.55, which also recorded the lowest standard deviation (SD = 0.72). This result informed a consistent

agreement among participants that the instructor provided timely progress reports using the Dashboard which supported self-regulated learning. Such consistency in feedback was highly valued by participants, highlighting the effectiveness of structured guidance in keeping students well-informed about their progress. Additionally, the aspect of 'facilitating discourse' was well achieved as strong perceptions were recorded for TP3 (M = 5.53, SD = 0.81) and TP9 (M = 5.53, SD = 0.79). They emphasised the instructor's organisational skills in communicating important deadlines and their empathy and care in supporting students emotionally.

These results demonstrate that both practical organisation and interpersonal sensitivity contributed meaningfully to students’ learning experiences.

Despite these positive outcomes, one area requiring improvement was identified in

TP7, which had the lowest mean score ($M = 5.43$, $SD = 0.79$). This suggests that participants felt the integration of innovative approaches for learning could be strengthened, highlighting opportunities for enhancing the instructional design further.

Table 4

Mean, and Standard Deviation of Students’ Perceived Teaching Presence

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall
TP1 The instructor clearly communicated important course goals for each task (in Google Docs).	5.44	0.83	
TP2 The instructor provided clear instructions on how to participate in this course learning activities (in Google Site & Google Classroom).	5.50	0.76	
TP3 The instructor clearly communicated important due dates/time frames for learning activities (in Google Classroom & WhatsApp Group).	5.53	0.81	
TP4 The instructor presented stimulating questions & answers (summary in Google Docs) that helped me to learn.	5.46	0.79	M= 5.49 SD= 0.71
TP5 The instructor helped keep the course participants on tasks (OI & CRW in Google Docs) in a way that helped me to learn.	5.50	0.80	
TP6 The instructor encouraged course participants to explore new concepts through the activities given in this course (in Google Docs).	5.45	0.87	
TP7 The instructor delivered course content in an innovative learning approach.	5.43	0.85	
TP8 The instructor provided a self-regulated learning progress report (using Dashboard) in the time needed.	5.55	0.72	
TP9 The instructor cared about my learning progress.	5.53	0.79	

Shared Metacognition (SM)

Table 5 presents the findings from the fifth section of the survey, which examined participants’ perceptions of self-regulation and co-regulation in the OCL environment. Overall, results indicate that the intervention was effective in fostering both individual and

collective metacognitive awareness, with mean scores of 5.28 for self-regulation and 5.34 for co-regulation. Standard deviation values remained consistently below 1.0 across all items, suggesting a high level of agreement among participants.

In terms of self-regulation (SM1 to SM6), participants reported strong awareness of their own learning processes during OCL activities. The highest mean scores were observed for SM1 (M = 5.46) and SM2 (M = 5.43), reflecting participants’ recognition of the effort they invested and the strategies they employed when working individually. By contrast, adaptability in learning strategies was slightly weaker, as shown in SM3 (M = 5.26). The lowest score emerged in SM4 (M = 5.06), indicating that some participants felt less confident in evaluating the difficulty of course content while engaging independently in metacognitive processes.

On the other hand, perceptions of co-regulation were notably strong. SM7 (M =

5.44) and SM8 (M = 5.42) highlighted participants’ ability to remain attentive to others’ ideas and to engage with group feedback during collaborative tasks. These results suggest that the OCL activities successfully encouraged learners to monitor and reflect on shared knowledge construction. Nevertheless, some variation was observed in SM9 and SM11, which measured participants’ comfort in observing peers’ strategies and in questioning additional information. Both items recorded relatively higher standard deviations (SD = 0.90 and 0.92), again demonstrating differences in how consistently participants experienced these aspects of group interaction.

Table 5

Mean, and Standard Deviation of Students’ Perceived Shared Metacognition

Items	Mean	Std. Deviation	Overall Self-Regulation & Co-Regulation	Overall Shared Metacognition
SM1 When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL, I am aware of my effort.	5.46	0.77		
SM2 When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL, I am aware of my thinking.	5.43	0.71	(Individual) Self-regulation: M = 5.28 SD= 0.87	M= 5.31 SD= 0.68
SM3 When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL, I question my thoughts.	5.26	0.87		
SM4 When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL,	5.06	0.98		

	I make judgement of the difficulty of the content provided.			
SM5	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL,	5.19	0.96	
	I change my strategy when I need to.			
SM6	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as an INDIVIDUAL,	5.27	0.91	
	I am aware of my level of learning.			
SM7	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP,	5.44	0.80	
	I pay attention to the ideas of others.			
SM8	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP,	5.42	0.77	
	I reflect upon the comments of others.			
SM9	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP,	5.26	0.90	
	I observe the strategies of others.			(Group)
SM10	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP,	5.35	0.87	Co-regulation: M = 5.34 SD= 0.85
	I look for confirmation of my understanding from others.			
SM11	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP,	5.20	0.92	
	I request/question further information from others.			
SM12	When I am engaged in the learning process (online collaborative learning (OCL) with course activities (OI & CRW)) as a member of a GROUP,	5.39	0.84	
	I respond to the contribution that others make.			

Discussion

Teaching Presence (TP)

The results indicated that TP was the most highly rated construct compared to SP, CP and SM. This suggests that participants placed strong value on the instructional strategies and guidance implemented within the OCL intervention. The consistently high mean scores across TP items informed the effectiveness of the instructor in managing learning, providing direction, and maintaining engagement.

A notable strength was the use of dashboard progress reports which offered participants timely updates on their learning progress and acknowledgement of performance. Such feedback provides not just clarity, but reassuring and motivating students to monitor their progress and supporting self-regulation. Morrison and Jacobsen (2023) similarly highlight that targeted feedback helps students recognise strengths and areas for improvement. As a result, students feel encouraged for continuous participation in online learning.

The design and organisation of the OCL environment was also highly regarded. Clear communication of course goals, task instructions, and deadlines helped participants manage their learning effectively. This aligns with Cottrell and Donaldson's (2013) view that while digital tools serve as delivery platforms, effective learning ultimately depends on structured guidance. Facilitating discourse was another key strength. Through guiding questions and reflective prompts, these strategies encouraged deeper exploration of course concepts, enabling participants to connect ideas critically. As Boettcher (2009) noted, purposeful facilitation fosters interaction and

promotes inquiry that forms an ideal OCL environment. Despite these positive outcomes, the lowest score was linked to innovation in teaching. Although participants valued the clarity and structure of the course, there was a desire for more creative and varied instructional approaches.

Shared Metacognition (SM)

On the other hand, SM was also highly perceived during the OCL intervention, with strong mean scores across both self-regulation and co-regulation. Standing out as the second most prominent construct after TP, the findings reflected its role in helping participants manage their own thinking while regulating group learning. In terms of self-regulation, participants showed strong awareness of their individual cognitive efforts, particularly in self-monitoring and goal setting. This is reflected in the findings by Wong et al. (2021) and Stephen and Rockinson-Szapkiw (2021), both emphasised goal commitment and progress tracking as essential for self-regulated learning. However, slightly lower scores in adaptability and confidence in evaluating content suggest that flexibility in adjusting strategies was less developed among the participants.

It is worth highlighting that perceptions of co-regulation were even more positive. Participants valued opportunities to engage with peers' ideas and feedback that fostered a sense of shared responsibility in collaborative tasks. These findings align with Yang et al. (2020), who showed that peer collaboration strengthens collective understanding, and Hadwin et al. (2017), who highlighted co-regulation as a significant process for improving strategies and learning outcomes. Overall, the OCL intervention successfully promoted both individual and shared

metacognitive practices. To further strengthen SM, future instructional designs was perceived to be emphasising on adaptability and flexible strategy use so that students are able to manage not only their own learning but also their contributions to collaborative knowledge building.

Cognitive Presence (CP)

The consistent strong perceptions for CP suggest that the OCL intervention effectively engaged students intellectually and supported their understanding of the Digital Audio and Video course content.

The exploration phase received the strongest perceptions, where participants reported that the OI-CRW activities exposed them to a variety of useful resources. This supports Kilinc and Altinpulluk (2021) who argued that structured peer learning tasks encourage students to share perspectives and engage with multiple viewpoints, thereby broadening their comprehension of the subject matter. The emphasis on exploration indicates that the OCL environment was effective in stimulating inquiry and critical engagement with content.

Similarly, the integration phase received positive perceptions, where the OI-CRW activities and reflective prompts supporting participants to connect new ideas with prior knowledge. This reflects Garrison et al.'s (2010) assertion that integration requires synthesising information to construct meaningful understanding. Moreover, the triggering event phase was also effectively implemented, with engaging materials capturing students' curiosity and stimulating inquiry (Garrison et al., 2001).

Despite the strengths, the resolution phase was less strongly perceived, mirroring findings by Jo et al. (2017), Galikyan and

Admiraal (2019), and Kaul et al. (2018), who collectively observed that online discussions often remain at exploration and integration stages. While participants agreed that OI-CRW activities supported idea development, lower scores suggest limited opportunities for authentic application of knowledge. As Zhai et al. (2024) noted, superficial engagement and reliance on uncritical prompts can hinder deeper cognitive processing.

Social Presence (SP)

Although SP was positively perceived overall, it emerged as the least strongly rated construct compared to the others. This finding contrasts with Akcaoglu and Lee (2016), who suggested that smaller group sizes typically strengthen interpersonal relationships in online learning. Among the SP categories, open communication was the most effectively facilitated. Consistent with Hoang and Hoang (2022) and Nasri et al. (2022), Google Docs provided an accessible platform for knowledge exchange and corrective feedback. According to Garrison & Akyol (2013), these behaviours are good indicator of open communication that establish mutual respect and trust, which, in turn, encouraged broader participation in the inquiry process.

Group cohesion was supported through collaborative features in Google Docs, such as commenting and real-time editing, which encouraged teamwork and acknowledgment of contributions (Hemati & Farahian, 2024; Tseng & Yeh, 2013). However, challenges were evident in managing disagreement. Survey results suggested that while collaboration was generally smooth, participants felt less comfortable addressing conflict, which weakened the overall sense of group cohesion. The lowest ratings were observed for affective expression, indicating

that the OCL environment was less effective in fostering belonging and interpersonal connection. This aligns with Arslan (2021), who argued that genuine social presence requires a foundation of belonging. In this study, peer interactions were often perceived as task-oriented rather than relationship-building, building a barrier the development of meaningful social bonds.

Limitation of Study

The main limitation of this study lies in its narrow focus on undergraduates enrolled in the course QMT213E Digital Audio and Video at a public university, in Penang, Malaysia. This restricted scope limits the generalisability of the findings, as the sample may not reflect the wider diversity of students across different institutions and academic levels in Malaysia. In addition, the intervention was tailored to a specific course context, which may reduce its applicability to other online courses with different content or learning objectives. Consequently, while the findings provide useful insights into the studied setting, their relevance to the broader landscape of online education in Malaysia remains limited.

Implications and Recommendations for Future Studies

This study shows that applying the CoI framework within an OCL intervention positively influenced students' perceptions of SP, CP, TP, and SM. For educators, the findings highlight the value of clear instructions, structured organisation, and timely feedback in sustaining student engagement. Student-centred practices that encourage reflection and self-monitoring also help learners take greater ownership of their progress. For students, the OCL experience fostered collaboration, critical thinking, and the development of metacognitive skills such as

goal-setting and co-regulation, ultimately contribute to more meaningful learning. For instructional designers, the study validates the use of Google tools, particularly Google Docs, as effective platforms for facilitating interaction and teamwork. These insights provide practical guidance for creating more engaging, inclusive, and supportive online learning environments.

Future studies may explore the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, such as educational chatbots, into OCL environments to further support the CoI constructs. AI-powered chatbots can serve as virtual facilitators that provide real-time feedback, scaffold inquiry, and prompt reflection, thereby strengthening both Teaching Presence and Cognitive Presence. For instance, chatbots embedded within collaborative platforms could guide students through reflective writing tasks, offer metacognitive prompts, or simulate peer questioning to enhance Shared Metacognition. Given that Social Presence received the lowest ratings in this study, AI-driven conversational agents may offer a promising avenue for sustaining interpersonal connection and emotional engagement beyond task completion. Research could also investigate how AI integration affects learners' perceptions of presence, regulation, and engagement across different disciplines and cultural contexts. Comparative studies between human-led and AI-supported facilitation may also yield insights into optimal instructional design for hybrid collaborative environments. Beyond AI integration, future studies could also investigate a wider range of collaborative learning activities, such as debates, case-based learning, and problem-based tasks, to examine how they influence the CoI constructs. Research could focus on different course contexts, including fully theoretical or fact-based subjects, to identify strategies

suitable for diverse disciplines. Testing alternative tools like Padlet or Miro may offer further insights into enhancing collaboration and reflective learning beyond Google Docs. Since Social Presence received the lowest ratings in this study, more emphasis should be placed on investigating community-building strategies that sustain meaningful interaction beyond task completion. Finally, examining the long-term effects of OCL interventions across varied institutions and student populations would broaden the generalisability of findings and deepen understanding of how the CoI framework can be effectively applied in different educational settings.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of an Online Collaborative Learning (OCL) intervention through the lens of the Community of Inquiry (CoI) framework, incorporating SP, CP, TP, and SM. The findings revealed overall positive perceptions, with TP rated highest and SP rated lowest, while SM emerged as a valuable extension to the CoI model. These results highlight the importance of clear guidance, structured activities, and collaborative reflection in fostering meaningful online learning. While the intervention effectively supported cognitive engagement and group collaboration, challenges remain in enhancing social connectedness and adaptability in learning strategies. Overall, the study contributes to extending the CoI framework by affirming the role of Shared Metacognition and offers practical insights for designing more engaging and holistic online learning environments.

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